

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE "PROJECTING" METHOD IN DEVELOPING THE COGNITIVE-PRAGMATIC COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14556911>

Abstract. *This article illuminates the significance of the "Design" method in the development of cognitive-pragmatic competencies of future elementary school teachers from a scientific and theoretical perspective. The article analyzes the scientific views of republican and foreign scientists on the "Projecting" method and provides methodological feedback.*

Keywords: *method, cognition, project, project work, method, stage, cognition, motivation.*

Introduction. One of the priority tasks of language education is the fundamental development and acceleration of science, technology, and economics in global education, the development of modern trends in working with information systems, the acquisition and generalization of information, as well as the development of cognitive-pragmatic competencies in future teachers based on innovative methods. From this perspective, special attention is paid to the speech, linguistic, cognitive-pragmatic competencies of future teachers in native language education, in particular, working with lexical, syntactic, morphological units of language levels, information, and their correct application in practical activities.

The development of modern approaches in the global language education system is based on the pedagogical and methodological improvement of cognitive-pragmatic competence, epistemology, working with information from various fields, being aware of scientific achievements and innovations, enhancing professional creativity, and achieving effectiveness in speech activities.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan LRU-637 "On Education" dated September 23, 2020 [1], the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated January 28, 2022 [2], and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-5847 "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 [3], The Presidential Decree PD-5349 "On Measures to Further Develop the Sphere of Information Technologies and Communications" dated February 19, 2018 [4], highlight that the implementation of effective management mechanisms in the higher education system, enhancing the scientific potential of graduates from higher educational institutions, and elevating their intellectual development to a qualitatively new level are considered crucial conditions. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of supporting the application of modern innovative forms and methods of education in the teaching and learning process. This underscores the relevance of researching the development of cognitive-pragmatic competencies of future teachers.

Discussion. The design method (project-based learning) is an educational form based on the pragmatic direction of pedagogy that ensures the design of practical assignments given to

students in the educational process and the demonstration of students' knowledge and skills in the process of their completion [5].

The design method is aimed at developing students' independent thinking and problem-solving skills in education. This method involves students in the project development process to solve a specific problem. The project stages typically include: task identification, solution development, practical research, and evaluation of results. This method serves to activate the practical activities of students in modern education and supports innovative educational processes. This method is also widely used in technical and scientific projects, such as the production of new products. The main advantages of the design method are the training of students to solve real problems and the development of their collaborative skills.

The term "design" entered pedagogy from the field of technology and means planning. The need to design the pedagogical process depends on the complexity of the educational content. Features of the task of practical classes based on the cooperation of student education in the higher education system at production enterprises: the development of internships at the enterprise according to the curriculum of the higher education system, the fact that cooperation includes several subjects, the choice of students, the fact that students are engaged in real (work) issues, that students receive assistance and support from various sources, that assessment is obtained from many sources (from production results) with the involvement of students themselves [6].

According to M.B. Urazova, the application of the design method in education serves the proper organization of the educational process for future specialists, the development of students' thinking, and the ability to anticipate the results achieved during the lesson. As a result, the quality and effectiveness of teaching will increase, and the professional competence of students will be formed. Regarding pedagogical design as a stage of creating innovative pedagogical projects, researchers rely on the following ideas: pedagogical design serves to prepare innovations introduced into the educational process more qualitatively; pedagogical design is a controlled process, based on the teacher's creativity, a system with a complex internal structure; pedagogical design has a variable character, implying a feedback relationship between the projected object and the teacher, carried out through experimental actions.

Working with future elementary school teachers on the project-based learning method is an effective educational strategy that serves to make the learning process for students interactive and interesting.

The stages of implementing the "project-based learning" method are as follows:

1. Select a topic: pay attention to the fact that the topic corresponds to the age characteristics and interests of students, as well as to the fact that it should be close to real life and related to practical activities.

2. Setting goals: the results that should be achieved through the project are determined. For example, the development of students' skills in group work, the enrichment of practical knowledge and experience, the development of independent thinking and problem-solving skills.

3. Step designation:

Stage of preparation: The purpose and plan of the project are explained.

Learning and research: Learners collect data on the topic.

Performance: students work on the project (drawing posters, making models, writing stories).

Presentation: Project results are presented in front of the classroom.

Analysis and evaluation: a joint review of the project's successes and failures.

Dividing into groups: uniting students with different abilities in each group, dividing students into small groups through the distribution of roles within the group (leader, writer, creator, etc.).

5. Resource provision: provide access to materials, libraries, or the internet necessary for students to work. Simple tools (paper, markers, scissors, stickers, etc.) should be sufficient for practical exercises.

6. Leadership and observation: Follow students, allowing them to work independently, providing assistance and guidance if necessary, but excessive intervention is harmful.

7. Evaluation of results: encouragement and demonstration of students' work (certificates, school exhibition). This helps them feel proud of their work.

There are certain differences between traditional methods and the "project-based learning" method in the educational process, indicating the achievements of the "project-based learning" method.

Differences	Traditional methods	Project based learning method
The focus of education	The teacher is in the center, and the students become passive listeners.	Students, as active participants, study the problem and create a solution.
Method of learning	It is aimed at memorizing ready-made knowledge.	It is used through self-study of knowledge and the solution of real problems.
Practice orientation	It is based on theoretical education.	Based on practical activities, students work on real projects.
Skills development	It is primarily based on assessment through tests or exams.	Develops skills in creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, and communication.
Motivation	Students work only to get grades.	Students understand the importance of projects and participate with greater interest.

As can be seen from the above, the "Projecting" method plays an important role in developing the cognitive-pragmatic competencies of future elementary school teachers. Through this approach, future teachers develop skills in independent thinking, creativity, and the ability to

solve real problems. The method ensures the practical application of theoretical knowledge and contributes to the development of cognitive competencies through their analysis, research, and collaborative work. The "Project-Based Learning" method is also an effective tool for strengthening students' speech, communication, and pragmatic skills.

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